

UNPATH'D WATERS: Experimental Public Value Evaluation

Evaluation Report: Work Package 6

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Preface

This short report sets out to test a new way of evaluating projects and programmes under the rubric of public value. The report has been researched and written by Shaheera Pesnani and Andy Brown of Historic England and forms an example of ‘rapid review’ in the terms of the Government guidance (HM Government 2019). It positions a public value-led evaluation as a type of process evaluation that considers how the programme was implemented with a view to assessing the extent to which public value was created. Its usefulness should be gauged in terms of (a) the ideas it may provoke about how similar projects might be implemented in future to optimise the value to the taxpayer, who has ultimately funded the research, and (b) the lessons learned by Historic England about public value as a prism through which to evaluate at least some of its projects and programmes in future. Thanks are due to the Unpath’d Waters colleagues who responded so promptly to the survey for their help. The responsibility for interpreting this and other evidence, of course, lies wholly with the authors.

1. Evaluating Research Reports

UKRI is committed to monitoring and evaluating its investments in order to maximise accountability and to learn ‘what works’. In line with the Government’s Magenta Book¹ guidance, these evaluations should be proportionate and ethical. Since it is often the case that impacts cannot be properly assessed until some considerable time after a project’s completion, research project evaluations that are undertaken within the timescale of a project or programme, like this one, largely focus on the process of the research rather than on its impact, although some prediction of likely impact may be possible.

The Magenta Book characterises process evaluation as ‘What can be learned from how the intervention was delivered?’ Process evaluation typically considers:

- Was the intervention delivered as intended?
- What worked well, or less well, for whom and why?
- What can be learned from the delivery methods used?
- How has the context influenced delivery?

These lines of inquiry work well for individual projects or for programmes of similar projects where findings can be generalised across the interventions. Evaluating a diverse group of projects in this way, however, is likely to lead to a number of somewhat disparate findings arising from separate analysis of each of the projects. For the Unpath’d Waters programme, therefore, an innovative approach was taken to the process evaluation in order to unite the evaluation into a coherent whole. To achieve this, Work Package (WP) 5 used the lens of shared values to look at how the other work packages delivered against the six stated values of the programme. This approach to evaluation gives more prominence to the ethical aspects of delivery than is often the case. The analysis has raised a variety of challenges to the way in which research is designed, funded, implemented and monitored².

¹ Magenta Book: Central Government Guidance on Evaluation (HM Treasury 2020)

² *Ethics as Practice: Report on the 1st Discovery Project Ethics Workshop* (Rutherford et al. 2024)

2. Introducing Public Value

An alternative approach for uniting a diverse group of projects using a single framework to facilitate comparison and contrast is to use the idea of public value. In 2019 the Government released a revised Public Value Framework³ (PVF) arising from Sir Michael Barber’s 2017 report into public value. Public value criteria were brigaded into four groupings, or pillars, which looked at the creation of public value from different but complementary perspectives (Fig. 1). The PVF was envisaged as being used in a number of ways, including taking stock of a policy or programme (ibid. para. 2.7). Table 3A of the revised Framework identifies ‘rapid review’ and ‘discrete review’ as potential approaches, taking in the region of 2-3 weeks and 4-6 weeks respectively.

Figure 1. The structure of the Government’s public value framework.

The concept of public value as a way of appraising the use of public investment was developed by US academic Mark Moore in the late 20th century⁴. It offered public sector managers a way of thinking about their practice that was analogous to private sector thinking while remaining relevant to the ethical and practical constraints of public administration. Instead of shareholder value, which is the goal of private enterprise, Moore offered the creation of public value as the measure of success for public sector enterprises. Public value is created when a given strategy or action has democratic legitimacy (e.g. the community supports it), when it has the support of the authorising environment (e.g. a governing board),

³ *Public Value Framework with supplementary guidance* (HM Government 2019)

⁴ *Creating Public Value: Strategic Management in Government* (Moore 1995)

and when the organisation has the operational capacity to implement the strategy or action effectively, not just in the short term but in a sustained manner.

3. Uses for Historic England’s PVF

In 2018 Historic England developed its own version of the Barber PVF, selecting from the original 152 challenges the 20 that were most relevant for its work, so bringing the concept more into the realm of practical use. Hitherto it has been used in a number of ways in Historic England, including assisting staff with their own research project designs, critiquing others’ project designs in the context of making funding decisions and developing new grant programmes such as the Everyday Heritage grants.

To give Historic England an option for a light-touch method for appraising the creation of public value, the ‘PVF-lite’ was introduced from the outset. This invited project designers and proposers, where the projects required relatively little public investment, to have convincing responses to just four of the 20 challenges – those shown in bold type at the head of each set of five challenges – those shown in bold type at the head of each set of five challenges in Figure 2.

The purpose of the PVF is not to seek to maximise but rather to optimise the creation of public value in the delivery of a project or programme. More public value can always be created at a cost, but the application of the PVF helps to judge the point at which the search for additional public value becomes disproportionate. In practice, feedback to project designers has therefore as often been to rein back on public value spend as it has been to spend more to create additional public value.

Figure 2: Historic England’s public value framework infographic.

At the outset, evaluation had been identified as one of the potential uses of the PVF but it has not previously been applied in this way. The application of the PVF as a lens for evaluating the Unpath'd Waters research programme is therefore a first for Historic England. The opportunity has been taken to experiment in this way in keeping with the spirit of innovative research that has characterised the whole Unpath'd Waters programme. Lessons learned from its pioneering application will be used in Historic England's future evaluation planning and is likely to be of assistance to other funders in the heritage sector such as the National Lottery Heritage Fund.

4. Key Evaluation Question (KEQ)

The Magenta Book emphasises the importance of precise evaluation questions in the design of effective evaluations; well-defined evaluation questions lead to the use of appropriate scoping, resources and methods for evaluation. KEQs should not be binary (yes/no) but open. They should be specific enough to help focus the evaluation, but broad enough to be broken down further into more detailed questions to guide data collection.

Bearing in mind the purpose of the PVF described above, in this case it was determined that the KEQ in this study was 'to what extent did the work packages optimise the creation of public value? The 20 challenges of the Historic England PVF could then be used to explore this overarching question. It was expected that not all of the 20 challenges would be applicable to each of the Unpath'd Waters work packages, but most should be. Furthermore, even when the challenges are applicable, it was expected that it would not always be possible, in the short time available, to adduce evidence to support the PVF appraisal. Missing data like these form one of the limitations of the analysis (see Section 8 below).

5. Methodology

The method used can be characterised as a rapid review, as set out in the Government's revised report on the Public Value Framework: 'Short, intense one-off assessment of what is already known about a policy or programme, by using systematic review methods to search and critically appraise existing research'.

The PVF appraisal involved a review of the Unpath'd Waters programme to determine how effectively the WPs created public value against Historic England's PVF. As stated in Section 3, applying the PVF as a tool for programme evaluation is an innovative approach for HE. Thus, understanding the PVF itself was the first step. The 20 challenges outlined in Historic England's PVF are broadly defined so that they can be applied in different contexts. It was essential, therefore, to understand how each question applied to the agreed-upon scope of the WPs to allow evidence to be gathered and assessed effectively.

A combination of primary and secondary research methods was employed. The primary research involved an online questionnaire distributed to individuals directly engaged in programme delivery, including the Senior Responsible Owner (SRO), Programme Manager, Lead Co-Investigator or Work Package Lead, and Communications Lead. The questionnaire gathered quantitative and qualitative insights into their experiences and perspectives on delivering the WPs. The questionnaire was open for responses for two weeks and received a remarkable 100% response rate.

The secondary research consisted of a review of the internal programme documents held by HE on its Sharepoint and the Unpath'd Waters website. At the outset, a thorough review of the documents was undertaken to identify the programme's objectives, activities and outputs, and gather any missing information.

Evidence, whether primary or secondary, was held up against a set of 'yardsticks' created for each of the PVF criteria to reach a consistent judgement on the degree to which the criteria had been satisfied. The yardsticks comprised four levels of compliance, level 1 being the weakest and level 4 the strongest. Where there was no evidence available within the timescale of the project, a nil return was recorded.

Using this method, average figures for each pillar were derived representing the degree to which the way that each Work Package was carried out created public value. This system-aided judgement provides a more reliable result than peer-aided judgement as the results are retraceable and relatively transparent.

Figure 3 (right). Example of the benchmarking used to rate each of the 20 PVF criteria. The term 'project' is interchangeable with 'programme'.

	Stakeholder needs
Green Score = 4	The project* identifies its key stakeholder groups and what they want
Green/amber Score = 3	The project* identifies its key stakeholder groups but not what they want
Amber/red Score = 2	The project* identifies only a sub-set of its key stakeholder groups and what they want
Red Score = 1	The project* appears unaware of its key stakeholder groups and what they want

6. Results

As mentioned in the above section, each of the six WPs of the Unpath'd Waters programme were scored against a set of PVF criteria to assess the nature and extent of public value created. Figure 2 describes the four pillars the WPs were judged on: Assured Alignment, Appropriate Resourcing, Public Support, and Capacity Development. An overview of the analysis is presented below. Individual criterion scores can be found in Appendix 1.

6.1 WP1: Aggregation and characterisation

The aim of this WP was to integrate the UK's marine heritage collections and make it accessible through the development of Unpath'd Waters portal. This WP was managed by the Archaeology Data Service at University of York.

According to the chart below (Fig.4), WP1 created the most public value under Pillar 3 (Public Support) by considering the needs of their stakeholders, public perceptions through social media and communications reporting, and the user experience of the Unpath'd Waters portal. Pillar 2 (Appropriate Resourcing) has scored the lowest as there wasn't enough information available about unit costs and financial management to ascertain the public value the WP has created. Under Pillar 1 (Assured Alignment), more public value could have been created had the focus of WP1 been more defined, which could have resulted in better engagement with other WPs and partners.

Figure 4: A summary of public value created by WP1

6.2 WP2: Discovery

The purpose of WP2 was to develop search methods to enhance the accessibility and aid the investigation of aggregated marine heritage datasets using Machine Learning techniques and methodologies. The University of Southampton was the lead for WP2.

According to the available evidence, WP2 closely aligned to its goals and outcomes, generating more public value in Pillar 1 (Assured Alignment) as compared to the other pillars (Fig 5). Due to limited and/or lack of evidence on public participation, communications reporting, and stakeholder influencing criteria, WP2 was assessed as creating less public value under Pillar 3 (Public Support). There also appeared to be a missed opportunity in terms of cross-boundary collaboration and evaluation of their outputs, which resulted in Pillar 4 (Capacity Development) contributing less to the public value overall rating.

Figure 5: A summary of public value created by WP2

6.3 WP3.1: People and the Sea

Led by the University of Portsmouth, this WP’s focus was on enhancing the significance of submerged and displayed wrecks (Mary Rose, Holland and The Needles) through audience engagement.

As is evident from Figure 6, WP3.1 was considered to have created more public value than WP1 and WP2. This was because WP3.1 not only stayed closely aligned to its goals and collaborated with other WPs under Unpath’d Waters programme but also benefited from cross-boundary collaboration, social media and communications reporting, engaging diverse audiences, evaluation of their activities, and being mindful of user experience. Despite struggling with timescales and resources, WP 3.1 was highly resilient.

Figure 6: A summary of public value created by WP3.1

6.4 WP3.2: Science and the Sea

Led by Bangor University, WP3.2 integrated scientific data with marine archives to identify and research wreck sites in the Irish Sea with high resolution multibeam sonar data.

WP3.2 created the most public value under Pillar 1 (Assured Alignment). The WP could have been rated more highly under Pillar 3 (Public Support) if evidence of stakeholder needs and influencing, public perception and participation had been found in the documents stored on the Sharepoint folder. Similarly, the WP scored lower under Pillar 4 (Capacity Development) due to staff resource challenges, which impacted engagement with other WPs and external collaborators, delivery and evaluation of outputs (Fig.7).

Figure 7: A summary of public value created by WP3.2

6.5 WP3.3: Lands beneath the Sea

This WP was led by University of Bradford and it was designed to make complex data representing submerged ancient landscapes, such as Doggerland, accessible to the public. As is evident from Figure 8, the WP has scored highest for its alignment with the outcomes of the programme. The WP’s novel approach of providing open access to an otherwise physically inaccessible landscape (it involved the creation of a simulation software, allowing users to navigate datasets regarding the submerged landscape under the North Sea) has enabled public participation using computer simulations, achieving a score just over 3 under Pillar 3 (Public Support).

Figure 8: A summary of public value created by WP3.3

6.6 WP4: Designing, Connecting, Immersing

The aim of this WP was to co-design an immersive tool (Navigator) to make maritime data more accessible to different audiences using VR technology. Figure 9 shows that WP4, led by the Glasgow School of Art, created the most public value under Pillar 4 (Capacity Development). The co-design workshops with the three key target audiences - visually impaired persons, non-coastal communities, and cross-disciplinary researchers – enabled WP4 to collaborate with diverse audiences and partners, use new technologies, and develop the technology based on the evaluation feedback received from the workshop groups. WP4 also performed particularly well under Pillar 3 (Public Support) and Pillar 1 (Assured Alignment). However, more value could have been created under Pillar 1 if more engagement was carried out with other WPs under Unpath’d Waters programme.

Figure 9: A summary of public value created by WP4

6.7 WP5: Audiences and evaluation

WP5 was led by the Museum of London Archaeology (MoLA) and was responsible for monitoring and evaluating shared values for the programme in line with the Digital Culture Charter, as well as metrics by which the programme was to hold itself accountable. The shared values informed the process of audience mapping to identify and articulate a programme of work for the overall project. Given the scope of WP5, judging it against the PVF was not felt to be appropriate or useful.

6.8 WP6: Programme Management

As the Lead Investigator of the Unpath'd Waters programme, Historic England maintained the overall management of the project. Given the ambitious nature of the programme, the structure of WP6 aided other WPs with their project delivery and outputs. The WP scored highly (Fig. 10) but could have created even more public value if more resource was allocated for project administration and communications reporting. WP6 has scored slightly higher under Pillar 2 (Appropriate Resourcing) compared with other WPs. This was because the evidence highlighted that WP6 set up the necessary processes and documents for WP leads to input data on financial management and unit costs, albeit that information was absent in the WP folders.

Figure 10: A summary of public value created by WP6

7. Conclusions

The key evaluation question that we set out to answer was ‘to what extent did the work packages optimise the creation of public value? Overall the PVF has proved useful in appraising the public value the Unpath’d Waters programme created but, in some cases, such as for WP5 and to some extent WP6, it was difficult to assess the WPs against all the challenges, as some questions were not useful for the purpose. However, thinking about the overall programme and where more public value could have been created:

- **Designing for public value:** Using PVF from the inception of the Unpath’d Waters programme would have allowed for continuous assessments against the framework; the programme management process could therefore have included the management of public value.
- **Lessons learned:** Some WPs underplayed evaluation of their work. While all WPs documented lessons learnt for quarterly highlight reports, a separate document or process that clearly captures the feedback loop into performance could have resulted in creating more value in this regard.
- **Training:** From the feedback received through the questionnaire, WP6 staff could have benefitted from relevant training on website editing and machine learning among other technical aspects to create more public value.
- **Staff resource and financial considerations:** WP3.2, 3.3, and 6 struggled with necessary staff resource to deliver the project. Lack of funding for administrative and communications support for WP6 appears to have limited the potential to create public value. In the case of WP3.3 funding for full-time posts instead of part-time researchers would have increased engagement with the project and timely delivery of goals, which could have created more public value.
- **Unit costs:** The capture of representative unit costs for activities under each of the WPs would allow future researchers to cost their proposals more reliably. Information on this aspect could have resulted in the programme creating more public value under Pillar 2.

- Financial management: WP6 maintained a document of Purchase Orders within their Sharepoint folder. Similar transparency in the other WPs would have been useful in scoring the WPs against Pillar 2 of the PVF. Some WPs (3.1, 4, and 5) benefitted from additional funding. Evidence in the other WPs of a detailed review of potential funding models would have allowed a higher public value rating under Pillar 2.
- Output recording: Some WPs were more active in reporting on their social media and communication activities, public participation, evaluation, and collaboration with stakeholders than other WPs. WP ratings of public value could have been higher if all WP leads had more accurately and promptly reported on all aspects of their work.
- Communications reporting: Each WP was responsible for their own social media activity. Detailed information on the posts, number of visitors and engagement, and some information on public engagement on the respective posts would have increased the public value ratings under Pillar 3.
- Engagement with other WPs: Almost all WP Leads said their work was informed or influenced by other WPs in the programme. WP3.2 was the exception to the rule; the WP lead recognised that they hadn't collaborated as much as they'd have liked to. Possibly due to existing workloads and strict timescales, an opportunity was lost to create value through more engagement with other WPs.
- Cross-boundary collaboration: There could have been more collaboration with other TaNC Discovery Projects. Out of 10 respondents, only 2 (WP5 and WP6) responded with a 'yes' to collaboration with other TaNC projects and 5 responded 'not as much as I'd have liked to.' This was a missed opportunity; more value could have been created if there was collaboration with other TaNC projects and/or external partners.

Comparison of the public value ratings (Appendix 2) suggests that the WPs all scored fairly well against the public value criteria but in different ways. One way of ranking the WPs in order to answer the key evaluation question is to average the average scores. This basic method puts WPs 3.1, 4 and 6 at the upper end of the order and suggests that WPs 2 and 3.2 could perhaps have been delivered in ways that created more public value. On this evidence, greater attention to stakeholder needs and user experience (Pillar 3) are areas for reflection for these two WPs.

As described in Section 3 above, the goal is not necessarily to maximise public value but to optimise it. Additional resources could have allowed extensive user involvement or technological innovation, for example, but this might have reached the point of diminishing returns, which drains rather than creates public value. Nevertheless, there were some areas, according to our appraisal, where a little extra activity could have added considerable value. The greatest variance in rating was seen in stakeholder influencing, which refers in particular to ensuring that stakeholders with authority and influence know about the successes of a project or programme and are inclined to champion the work in their spheres of influence. This is not an expensive task but could make a big difference to the way the programme is perceived and to the future funding of similar work.

8. Limitations

Owing to time constraints, it was not feasible to carry out an in-depth evaluation. This analysis does not, therefore, provide a comprehensive assessment of how Unpath'd Waters has created public value. Instead, it is a pointer to an alternative approach to the evaluation of diverse programmes and an attempt to provoke further thought and discussion about the evaluation of research projects and programmes.

The sample size for the scope of this evaluation process was limited to key individuals: SRO, Project Manager, WP Lead, and Comms Manager. However, it would have been beneficial to conduct wider consultations in the form of interviews and/or focus group discussions with Research Assistants, Collaborators, Partners, Advisory Group, and members of the public who participated in the planning and co-designing of the WPs to fully grasp the impact, legacy and value of the programme.

The lack of relevant information on WP management - including but not limited to financial management, unit costs of work, consistent media and communication reporting, and stakeholder perceptions - made it challenging to evaluate some of the WPs, if not all, against the PVF criteria. Where evidence was unavailable no rating was made against the criterion; the average rating for that pillar was not affected.

9. Recommendations

Based on the appraisal of the Unpath'd Waters programme against PVF, two sets of recommendations have emerged – one intended more for AHRC/UKRI, the other more for Historic England.

9.1 Recommendations for AHRC

- a) To consider utilising public value itself as a tool for designing and appraising research programmes.
- b) To remind individuals and organisations seeking funding that a public value framework has been adopted by the Government as a useful and important tool to design and evaluate research projects.
- c) To consider compiling a data bank on unit costs for different types of research: prospective researchers and project appraisers would find it useful if information on unit costs was available as it would illustrate the expected range of costs to carry out a similar research project and thus assist with costing new proposals.

9.2 Recommendations for Historic England

- a. Using our PVF as an evaluation tool for Unpath'd Waters programme shows that PVF can be an effective appraisal tool. Therefore, it is recommended that we continue experimenting with PVF for other HE evaluations, as the initial indication of usefulness has proved to be positive.
- b. A final recommendation is for the Programme team. We noted in our appraisal under Pillar 3 that there was sometimes a lack of targeted communication aimed at influencing key stakeholders (such as DCMS or coastal MPs) by ensuring that they were aware of the remarkable successes of the WPs. We hope that, before the programme is finally closed down, this might yet be possible.

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